

How the Interface Controls the Properties of Fibre Composites

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ABSTRACT

The excellent mechanical properties of fibre composites can only be realized if we can transfer stresses effectively from fibres to matrix. The interface is subject to very high shear stresses, even when the stress applied to the composite is quite small. It has a low work of fracture, so can fail at low applied stresses. Subsequent behaviour is then governed by sliding friction under an interfacial pressure determined by the method and conditions of manufacture of the composite. The consequences of interface failure and subsequent slip are discussed in relation to modulus, strength (tensile, compression, shear and off-axis), toughness, environment effects, fatigue, and creep of fibre composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern fibre composite was invented in 1944 when aircraft randomes were made of glass reinforced polyester. This composite, being much better than earlier composites, has displaced them almost entirely, displaced metals, and led to the development of a whole family of reinforced plastics. As a result, the plastics industry has been growing quickly, and in several countries, is fast outstripping the metals industry in numbers employed, (7% of the total employed in the U.S. and Canada) and fraction of the gross national product generated (11% of the GNP).

By virtue of their high modulus, and high strength, coupled with light weight, composites are already the material of choice in many load bearing situations. As the possibilities for efficient design and economical construction become more widely appreciated, we can expect that metals will be replaced by composites in most applications where their special properties, such as electrical conductivity, high temperature resistance, hardness, and erosion resistance, are not needed.

Fibre composites work well because the fibres are usually long enough that the stresses can be transferred adequately between the polymer and the fibres. However, there are some fibre composites that have strengths which are lower than the strength of the unreinforced matrix, as can be readily verified by examining the plastics Encyclopedia (1). These composites have very short fibres, which are randomly oriented.

Stresses are transferred across the fibre-matrix interface, and this process controls many properties of the composite, in addition to strength and modulus. Unfortunately, data on the parameters controlling stress transfer are sparse. Thus we usually do not know what fibre length to classify as 'short', and what constitutes a 'long' fibre, when it comes to reinforcing a plastic.

This paper examines the properties of a composite that are affected by the fibre-matrix interface. Attention is directed mainly to aligned fibre composites, since these are more easily understood than random fibre composites. Interlaminar interface effects in laminates, although of great importance (2) will not be discussed here for reasons of brevity.

2. THE NATURE OF THE FIBRE AND THE INTERFACE

Real composites have fibres which are approximately cylindrical in shape, and have jagged ends. Any discussion of practical composite materials must take into account variations in fibre diameter, lack of perfect roundness, and the stress-raising nature of the fibre end.

The fibres are often coated with an adhesion promoter. With glass fibres, silanes are used. These form strong adhesive bonds to the glass through hydrogen bonding or Van der Waals bonding (3). Covalent bonding between the adhesion promoter and the glass is not necessary, since the polymers themselves are held together largely by hydrogen and Van der Waals bonds. The adhesion promoter usually has a reactive group which can react with, and become part of, the polymer structure, during curing of the resin, when a glass reinforced thermoset is being made. It is very important that the glass has the appropriate coating for the resin being used, because this reaction is specific to the polymer.

The technology of adhesion promotion for carbon reinforced plastics does not appear to have reached such an advanced stage as it has in the case of glass. Adhesion between carbon and plastics is not strong because of the inert nature of the carbon. Mechanical keying is therefore promoted by roughening the fibre by etching with strong acids, or using oxygen at high temperature. These processes appear to make the surface more reactive, as well as more rough. Adhesion promoters are also used, but they are not usually specific; i.e. the same promoter is often used for epoxy and polyester resin.

Kevlar fibres are presently used without adhesion promoters in polyester resins, but with promoters in epoxies.

Pull-out tests (4) on single glass fibres embedded in a polyester resin show that the adhesive bond has a work of fracture of about 90 Jm^{-2} , so that a fibre stress of 2.6 GPa is required to initiate sliding of a $20 \mu\text{m}$ diameter fibre embedded to a depth of 1.3 m. The work of fracture predominates over the shear stress required to break the polymer at the interface. Sliding is controlled by friction, and lack of perfection in the fibre surface has an important effect on this. The friction force is governed by the coefficient of friction, and the pressure between fibres and matrix caused by cure shrinkage of the matrix. Fig. 1 shows pull out curves obtained with $20 \mu\text{m}$ diameter E glass fibres in epoxies and polyester, together with a theoretical curve for a fibre with a perfect surface. The effect of destroying the adhesion and reducing the friction by the use of a silicone oil is also shown.

If the fibre is embedded to a depth greater than about 50 diameters it will pull out for about 5 diameters, as the adhesion fails, and then break because the friction forces quickly become larger than the force that was required to fracture the bond.

Work with steel fibres enabled both coefficient of friction and interfacial pressure to be determined independently. The pressures were unexpectedly low, i.e. 3 MPa for epoxy and 7 MPa for polycarbonate (5). The corresponding coefficients of friction were 0.19 and 0.6 respectively.

For the epoxy resin shown in fig. 1, the pressure is about 20 MPa, since the pull-out curve in this case has approximately zero slope when the fibre stress is about 2.5 GPa. With the polyester resin the low fibre stress in the zero slope region, i.e. about 1.5 GPa, suggests that the pressure is only about 12 MPa. Since the final slope, when pull out is almost complete, implies an interfacial shear stress, τ_i of about 24 MPa, the coefficient of friction in this case is very high, i.e. about 2.0.

Fig. 1. Fibre pull-out curves (4)

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves (8,9)

3. COMPOSITE MODULUS AND THE STRESS-STRAIN CURVE

The standard treatments for composite modulus assume that fibres and matrix remain tightly bound together, so that no slip occurs. However, it has been known for a long time (6) that, in fact, high stresses quickly develop at the fibre ends, so that failure of the matrix or the fibre-matrix interface must occur when quite small stresses are applied to the composite.

It can easily be shown that real composites, which do slip, do nevertheless behave approximately linearly, so long as the fibres are long enough. This is because the stress-strain relationship for an aligned fibre composite, in which fibres slip, is given to a first approximation by (7).

$$\sigma_1 = E_1 \epsilon_1 - A \epsilon_1^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, σ_1 and ϵ_1 are the composite stress and strain in the fibre direction, and E_1 is the Rule of Mixtures modulus. A is a constant which is inversely proportional to the fibre aspect ratio. A becomes very small when the fibre aspect ratio becomes large, and thus continuous fibre composites obey the expression $\sigma_1 = E_1 \epsilon_1$.

With short fibres, the quadratic approximation for the stress-strain curve works well over a range of strains. At both high and low strains deviations occur, but for different reasons. Fig. 2 shows some experimental results for a random fibre composite (8), and for comparison, some curves drawn using a recent slip theory for a random composite (9). The experimental curve can be reproduced quite accurately if appropriate values are chosen for the unknown constants, such as the interfacial shear stress. Quadratic expressions can also be used to fit the appropriate parts of the stress-strain curves for aligned fibre composites (10, 11).

We will now examine the factors which determine the onset of slip. We can recognize three criteria for slip: 1) an energy criterion similar to the Griffith fracture criterion; 2) a stress criterion based on shear lag analysis; and 3) a criterion for microslip based on the stress concentrations arising from the sharp corners at the ends of the fibres.

The energy criterion requires that the strain at the slip point, ϵ_{1e} must

exceed a certain value:

$$\epsilon_{1e} \geq 8G/dE_f \quad (2)$$

Here G is the work of fracture of the interface, d is the fibre diameter, and E_f is the fibre Young's modulus. For glass, Kevlar, and carbon reinforced polymers this criterion should be easily satisfied for $\epsilon_{1e} < 0.1\%$, since the measurements described in section 2 indicate that G is unlikely to exceed about 100 Jm^{-2} .

The stress criterion, which, with sufficient accuracy for our present purposes, can be determined from Cox's early work (12) gives (13)

$$\epsilon_{1s} \approx 2\tau_a / \sqrt{E_f E_m} \quad (3)$$

Where E_m is the Young's modulus of the matrix and τ_a is the shear stress required to fracture the interface, or the adjacent matrix. For ductile polymer matrices τ_a will not exceed half the matrix tensile strength (typically 70 MPa), and in this case $\epsilon_{1s} \approx 0.5\%$ for glass composites, 0.4% for Kevlar composites and 0.22% for stiff carbon composites. Since the energy criterion is also satisfied, we must conclude that slip starts at very small strains. This slip will occur even when the fibres are continuous.

This observation provides a good justification for the strain limited design method frequently used with fibreglass structures. In this, the wall thickness of the structure is designed so that the strain is 0.1%, or sometimes 0.2%. These values are well below the slip point strain given by equation 3.

The stress concentration arising from the sharp corners at the fibre ends has been shown to be several times the shear lag stress. (14,15). Thus some slip can occur before ϵ_{1s} (equation 3) is reached. It will not take place at strains less than ϵ_{1e} (equation 2), and St. Venant's principle suggests that it will be effective over very small distances (less than one fibre diameter). The actual distance will depend on the radius of the corner at the fibre end.

Fig. 3 indicates the various processes taking place at low strains. The

Fig. 3. Regions of stress-strain curves

Fig. 4. Theoretical stress-strain curves effect of fibre aspect ratio (17)

first region, for $\epsilon_1 < 0.1\%$, is entirely elastic, and governed by fibre and matrix Young's moduli, and volume fractions, V_m and V_f :

$$\sigma_1 \approx (V_f E_f (1 - \sqrt{E_m/E_f}/s) + V_m E_m) \epsilon_1 \quad (4)$$

This approximate equation, s being the fibre aspect ratio, is accurate enough for most purposes (13). The microslip region will also be adequately described by equation 4, since most of the interface is still intact. When $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_{1s}$, however, the slip becomes more significant. The fraction of fibre that is slipping, m , is given by

$$m = E_f \epsilon_1 / 4\tau_i s \quad (5)$$

(m is equivalent to the 'strain dependant critical length' used by some authors (16)). At this point the stress-strain curve is governed by equation 1, and

$$A = V_f E_f^2 / 4\tau_i s \quad (6)$$

Stress-strain curves can be predicted using this dual approach, i.e. a simple elasticity treatment for strains less than ϵ_{1s} , and slip treatment for higher strains. If greater accuracy is desired, the residual elastic effects near the fibre mid point should be included, as also should Poisson's shrinkage effects. This approach leads to some important results (17).

Fig. 4 shows the effect of fibre aspect ratio in an aligned carbon-epoxy using plausible values for the unknown parameters, such as matrix shrinkage stress and the interfacial friction coefficient. The curves are terminated when $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_{fu}$, the fibre breaking strain, for fibre aspect ratios greater than the critical values, s_c . ($s_c = \sigma_{fu} / 2\tau_i$ where σ_{fu} is the fibre tensile strength). For fibres with $s < s_c$, m reaches 1.0 before ϵ_1 reaches ϵ_{fu} . In this case the load carried by the fibres does not change once $m = 1$ (note that $m \neq 1$) and the matrix slips continuously past the fibres.

Fig. 5. Composite modulus and strength (13)

Fig. 6. Effect of adhesion parameter, a , (17)

The corresponding effect of aspect ratio on modulus for $\epsilon_1 < \epsilon_{1s}$ is shown in fig. 5. Note that for $s > 20 E_f/E_m$ the composite obeys the Rule of Mixtures within 5%. This is the case for glass composites when $s > 110$, for Kevlar when $s > 150$, and stiff carbon when $s > 250$.

Figs. 4 and 5 were drawn for τ_i equal to half the matrix tensile strength. If the adhesion is not perfect τ_i will be much less than this, and ϵ_{1s} will be correspondingly reduced. We will let $\tau_i = a\sigma_{mu} / 2$, where a is an adhesion parameter ($a < 1$). We can now plot the effect of adhesion as shown in fig. 6, for the same carbon-epoxy.

Two other parameters have important effects on the stress-strain curves. Fig. 7 shows the effect of the interfacial friction coefficient, and fig. 8 the effect of the interfacial pressure, for carbon having $s = 200$.

Some progress has been made in adapting slip theory for random fibre composites (9) some of the results of this are shown in the theoretical curves in fig. 2.

4. COMPOSITE STRENGTH

Composites with aligned fibres which are not too short fail at the fibre breaking strain, ϵ_{fu} , so long as the fibre volume fraction is greater than the critical value, V_{fmin} (It should be noted that V_{fmin} is greater for random fibres than it is for aligned fibres (18)). Composite strength, σ_{1u} , is thus given by the well-known expression.

$$\sigma_{1u} = (V_f(1-s_c/2s) + V_m E_m/E_f)\sigma_{fu} \tag{7}$$

obtained by putting $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_{fu}$ into equation 1 with A given by equation 6. In figs 6,7,8 the curves are terminated at ϵ_{fu} , except for very short fibres with $s < s_c$.

The interface affects the composite strength directly through its effect on s_c . Pull out measurements on glass in polyester and epoxy give variable τ_i values roughly about 20 MPa, while fibre strengths were often about 4 GPa. Thus $s_c \approx 200$. Consequently, we cannot expect to get composite strengths close to the Rule of Mixtures value (within 5% say), unless $s = 2000$. The corresponding fibre length is 4 mm for these glass fibres, which have a diameter of 20 μ m.

Fig. 7. Effect of friction coefficient (17)

Fig. 8. Effect of matrix shrinkage stress (values are GPa) (17)

The interface has a direct effect on compressive strength. Fig. 9 shows the results of experiments with carbon (19) and glass (20). If we assume that the fibres in a composite are never completely straight, this effect can be accounted for (21). When the composite is compressed, the convex side of the fibre pushes against the matrix, and the concave side exerts a corresponding pull. If the adhesion at the interface is poor, separation can take place on the concave side, leading to splitting of the composite, followed by buckling failure. This separation also accounts satisfactorily for the lower modulus in compression of carbon fibre pultruded rods (21).

The interface also has a direct effect on the shear strength of aligned fibre composites, fig. 10 (22). The failure stress, τ_{12u} , will be determined by the relative cross sections of interface, A_i , and matrix, A_m ; thus

$$\tau_{12u} \approx A_i \tau_i + A_m \tau_{mu} \tag{9}$$

In a regularly packed arrangement, e.g. square or hexagonal, we can use the 'packing factor', P_f . ($P_f = \pi$ for square packing and $P_f = 2\pi/\sqrt{3}$ for hexagonal packing (23)). For a failure which crosses the matrix along the narrowest parts

between the fibres, and goes around the fibre surface, $A_i = \pi\sqrt{V_f/P_f}$ and $A_m = 1 - 2\sqrt{V_f/P_f}$. Thus a pultruded rod, for example, which has very little adhesion, so that $\tau_i \ll \tau_m$, made with a ductile epoxy with a tensile strength of 70 MPa can have a shear strength of as little as 7 MPa.

Analogous results are obtained for the strength in directions at right angles to the fibres. In this case we can use

$$\sigma_{2u} \approx \sigma_{3u} \approx A_i \sigma_{iu} + A_m \sigma_m \quad (10)$$

where σ_{iu} is the tensile strength of the interface. The above pultruded rod would have a strength of only about 13 MPa along directions in the 2-3 plane.

With brittle matrices a fracture criterion for shear and transverse failure is more appropriate.

In the case of random fibre composites failure probably occurs when the fibres aligned in the stress direction suffer a certain amount of gross slip ($m = 1$ and $\epsilon_1 > 2\tau_s/E_f$). This gives the type of decrease of failure strain with fibre aspect ratio reported by Curtis et al (16). There is a region at the high strain end of the stress-strain curve where the quadratic expression (equation 1) is not obeyed. A matrix fracture approach (24) can be used to explain this, and has recently been developed to take more account of interface effects (25).

Fig. 9. Compression strengths, aligned carbon fibre (19) and aligned glass fibre (20) composites

Fig. 10. Effect of fibre coating in carbon fibre composites (22)

5. TOUGHNESS

In carbon and glass fibre composites, since the fibres are so brittle, and the matrix ductility is suppressed (26) the interfaces are the most important contributors to the work of fracture. In laminates, interlaminar interfaces play an important role (27), but in pultruded rods, and other non-laminated structures, the fibre-matrix interface is of paramount importance. This subject has been reviewed (28) but there has been an important development recently with the realization of the role played by the matrix shrinkage stress (29). Fig. 11 shows that toughness of carbon-epoxies can be increased substantially by control of matrix shrinkage. This patent method (30) may go a long way to improve the toughness of carbon fibre composites, when other methods (27) are not available.

Fibres with the critical aspect ratio make the toughest composites, unless ductile fibres (e.g. Kevlar) are used. The toughness, G_{fpm} , is then

$$G_{fpm} = V_f d\sigma_{fu}^2 / 24\tau_i \quad (11)$$

If the fibres are randomly orientated the work of fracture can be quite large, but depends on the matrix yield stress as well as the fibre-matrix interface (31). The increased toughness resulting from the decrease in τ_i brings with it the decrease in off-axis properties previously mentioned: fig. 10 shows the effect when fibres are continuous. It can also lead to excessive crack openings and loss of structural integrity (31).

6. ENVIRONMENT EFFECTS

Glass fibre composites are degraded by water, unless the fibre surface is well protected (3). This is perhaps the main role played by the silanes used in coupling agents. The hydrogen (or Van der Waals) bond developed by the silane is strong enough to resist the strong tendency for water to form hydrogen bonds.

Since substantial slip takes place near the fibre ends once ϵ_{1s} is exceeded, there is a danger of attack of the interface there when $\epsilon_{1s} > \epsilon_{1s}$. Consequently fibreglass should not be used in a water environment when the ϵ_{1s} strain exceeds about 0.5%, since water, once established at the fibre ends, could exert pressure there, and thus extend the slipped region. The design strain for glass reinforced polymers provides for a degree of safety here, which will also be needed to prevent attack in the microslipped regions near the corners at the fibre ends.

Fig. 11. Effect of controlling matrix shrinkage stress (13)

Fig. 12. Fatigue curves for reinforced epoxies (35,36,37)

Similar precautions are required with other systems designed for use in reactive environments. With carbon-epoxies, strains should be kept below 0.22%, and with Kevlar below 0.4%, when the fibre surface has a strong affinity for the reactive agent.

Ductile layers on the fibre surface have been shown to be effective in improving the off-axis strength (33).

7. FATIGUE

It has been known for some time that fatigue failure of composites occurs in three states, 1) interface failure, 2) matrix cracking and 3) total separation (34). Comparative data for the first two stages, for different fibres, but for the same geometry, do not appear to be readily available. We can, however, plot total separation for different fibre systems, in order to make comparisons of specific fatigue effects, as shown in fig. 12.

Fig. 12 is a plot of the fatigue failure stress, as a fraction of the static strength, vs number of cycles to failure. It can be seen that boron fares best and glass worst in this comparison. We conclude that interface effects may be playing an important role in the fatigue process, since for glass ϵ_{1s} is about eight times ϵ_{1s} , while for boron and carbon it is only about four and five times

ϵ_c respectively. Thus, more slip is taking place in the glass composite than the boron and carbon composites, and this probably accounts for the steeper slope in fig. 12. Kevlar is similar to glass, with $\epsilon_c \sim \epsilon_{1s}$, but is ductile, so cannot be directly compared with glass, carbon or boron.

Ductile layers have been shown to be effective in improving the fatigue life of glass reinforced epoxies (33).

8. CREEP

For stresses in the fibre direction, continuous aligned carbon and glass reinforced polymers have excellent creep properties (38) because the fibres are highly creep resistant. Kevlar fibres creep (39), so composites made with these fibres are not so creep resistant.

For aligned short fibre composites, creep effects are expected for stresses in the fibre direction because the fibre sizing, and the polymer adjacent to the fibres are viscoelastic materials, and are under high stress near the fibre ends. Thus under creep conditions, τ_i is decreased, and hence s_c is increased. This will increase the strain at any given stress (equation 1) and will decrease the failure stress (equation 7).

For off-axis stresses, and for non aligned fibre composites, large creep effects are observed because of the poor creep resistance of the matrix.

9. CONCLUSION

Many important properties of fibre composites are strongly affected by the interface between fibre and matrix. In view of this central role played by the interface, it is surprising that so few data on τ_i , the coefficient of friction, the pressure, and the work of fracture of the interface, are available.

The principal method of measuring interface properties is the fibre pull-out tests (40). Indirect data comes from tests on single fibres (41) or a few fibres embedded in polymers, while shear tests and compression tests can be used as qualitative tests of interfaces in pultrusions, and laminates, etc.

There is presently a great need for more tests to determine the efficacy of fibre surface treatments, the effect of active environments such as water, the effect of heat, etc. Also, more advanced tests are needed to evaluate the more basic parameters, i.e. the friction coefficient, the pressure, and the work of fracture. Work is already proceeding on this (42).

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